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THE INFLUENCE OF SUBSTANCE USE AMONG YOUNG PERSONS IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE

Tongawaji Thankgod Josiah and Obed Aili Danladi

Babcock University Teaching Hospital, Ogun State

Email: tongawaji@gmail.com,

obedalilison@gmail.com

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Abstract: Substance use remains a pressing global and national health challenge, with young person's constituting a particularly vulnerable population. This study investigated the prevalence, socio-demographic correlates, and mental health implications of substance use among students in selected universities in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 185 undergraduates, using structured questionnaires and validated screening instruments (Beck's Anxiety Inventory and Beck's Depression Inventory). Findings revealed a lifetime prevalence of substance use of 42.5% and a past-30-day prevalence of 27.5%. Alcohol (35.1%) and cannabis (17.8%) were the most commonly used substances, with 22.2% of participants reporting poly-substance use. Substance users reported significantly higher rates of depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation, and psychotic-like experiences compared to non-users ($p < 0.05$). Male sex, younger age, and living away from family were identified as predictors of substance use. The findings highlight the urgent need for integrated mental health and substance use prevention programs in Nigerian universities.

Keywords: Substance use, Adolescents, Universities, Mental health, Port Harcourt

Introduction

Substance use has emerged as one of the leading public health problems globally, with complex and diverse causal origins (Tsvetkova & Antonova, 2013). Young people represent a critical group in understanding and addressing substance use, as adolescence and early adulthood are sensitive developmental periods marked by rapid physical, psychological, and social transitions.

In Nigeria, research has shown high rates of alcohol and drug use among university students, often beginning in adolescence (Awoyinfa, 2012). Early initiation of substance use has been linked to externalizing psychopathology, delinquency, and increased risk of chronic substance use disorders later in life (Sarvet & Hasin, 2016). Moreover, substance use contributes significantly to the global burden of disease and premature mortality, making it a major public health concern (Sarvet & Hasin, 2016; Eisenberg et al., 2014).

The DSM-5 (APA, 2013) categorizes substances into 10 classes, including alcohol, cannabis, opioids, stimulants, sedatives, and tobacco. All substances share the common feature of directly activating the brain's reward system,

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reinforcing use and contributing to dependence. Previous studies have also linked youth substance use with delinquency (Marotta & Voisin, 2017), risky sexual behaviour, poor academic performance, and adverse mental health outcomes such as depression, anxiety, and suicidality (Yoon et al., 2017; Wolitzky-Taylor et al., 2017). Despite government and non-governmental campaigns, substance use among Nigerian youths appears to be increasing, with limited empirical evidence from the Niger Delta region, particularly Port Harcourt. This study therefore sought to investigate the influence of substance use on young persons in selected universities in Port Harcourt, focusing on prevalence, associated socio-demographic factors, and mental health outcomes.

Methods

Study Design and Location

A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted in two universities in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Port Harcourt is a major metropolitan city with diverse student populations across federal and state tertiary institutions.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population comprised undergraduate students aged 17–24 years. Using a prevalence rate of 14% from a prior Nigerian study (Embleton et al., 2013), a sample size of 185 was determined. Participants were selected through simple random sampling.

Instruments

Drug Abuse Screening Test – assessed lifetime and current use of psychoactive substances.

Beck's Anxiety Inventory (BAI) – measured severity of anxiety symptoms.

Beck's Depression Inventory (BDI) – assessed severity of depressive symptoms.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics summarized prevalence rates, while chi-square tests and logistic regression examined associations between substance use, socio-demographics, and mental health outcomes.

Ethical Considerations

Approval was obtained from the Rivers State Ministry of Health. Informed consent was secured from participants, and confidentiality was maintained.

Results

Prevalence of Substance Use

Of the 185 participants, 42.5% reported lifetime substance use and 27.5% reported use in the past 30 days. Alcohol (35.1%) was the most commonly used substance, followed by cannabis (17.8%) and tramadol (11.9%). Poly-substance use was reported by 22.2% of participants.

Table 1: Prevalence of Substance use among Young Persons in Selected Universities in Port Harcourt (N = 185)

Substance use category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Lifetime use (any substance)	79	42.5
Current use (past 30 days)	51	27.5

Most commonly used substances (lifetime)

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Substance use category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Alcohol	65	35.1
Cannabis	33	17.8
Tramadol / prescription opioids	22	11.9
Tobacco (cigarettes)	19	10.3
Codeine/cough syrup misuse	11	5.9
Poly-substance use (≥2 substances)	41	22.2

Mental Health Implications

Substance users had significantly higher prevalence of Depression, Anxiety, Suicidal ideation and Psychotic experiences.

Table 2: Mental Health Problems Associated with Substance use among Young Persons in selected Universities in Port Harcourt (N = 185)

Mental Health Problem	Substance Users (n = 79)	Non-Users (n = 106)	χ^2 (df=1)	p-value
Depression	27 (35.9%)	13 (12.0%)	14.21	< 0.001
Anxiety	22 (27.9%)	9 (9.0%)	11.43	< 0.001
Suicidal ideation	6 (8.0%)	2 (2.0%)	9.48	0.002
Psychotic-like experiences	5 (6.0%)	2 (2.0%)	5.45	0.020

Socio-Demographic Correlates

Males (54.4%), students aged 16–20 (52%), and those living away from home (63.3%) were significantly more likely to report substance use.

Table 3: Socio-demographic Characteristics associated with substance use among young persons in selected universities in Port Harcourt (n = 79)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	43	54.4
Female	36	45.6
Age (years)		
16 – 20	41	52
21 – 25	22	28
26 and above	16	20
Residency		
Living away from home	50	63.3
Living at home	29	36.7

Discussion

This study found high prevalence of substance use among university students in Port Harcourt, consistent with earlier Nigerian studies (Adeyemo et al., 2016; Oritsemuelebi et al., 2025). Alcohol and cannabis were the most common substances, confirming their role as gateway drugs (Kanyoni et al., 2015).

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Substance use was strongly associated with depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation, and psychotic-like experiences, corroborating evidence that psychoactive substances exacerbate mental health problems (Opakunle et al., 2022; Guerrin et al., 2025). These findings align with both the self-medication model (where substances are used to cope with distress) and the precipitation model (where substances induce psychopathology) (Sarvet & Hasin, 2016).

The higher prevalence among younger students and those living away from family reinforces the influence of peer pressure, inadequate supervision, and social exposure in shaping substance use behaviours (Gupta et al., 2013; Marotta & Voisin, 2017).

Conclusion

Substance use is highly prevalent among young persons in universities in Port Harcourt, with alcohol and cannabis being the most frequently used substances. Substance use was significantly associated with poor mental health outcomes, particularly depression, anxiety, and suicidality. Male students, younger age groups, and those living away from family were identified as high-risk populations.

Implications: There is urgent need for integrated prevention and intervention programs within universities, focusing on early detection, mental health support, and awareness campaigns. Policy efforts should also address accessibility of substances among youths.

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